

EXPERIMENTAL OBSERVATIONS OF THE SPRING-BACK PHENOMENON

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ABSTRACT

The deformations of organic matrix composites caused by manufacturing stresses are investigated by measuring the spring-back of L-shaped 90 degree elbows made of unidirectional, cross ply, angle ply, and quasi-isotropic symmetric laminates. Data are given showing the effects on spring-back of ply lay-up, laminate thickness, corner radius, and fiber volume fraction. Of these factors, the fiber volume fraction at the corner has the largest influence on spring-back.

I. INTRODUCTION

It is well known that curved composite laminates change their shapes when they are cooled down after manufacturing. This phenomenon, commonly referred to as spring-back, must be taken into account in designing the mold and the part. For proper design, the factors influencing the spring-back phenomenon must be understood. In this paper, data are given which shed light on the importance of some of the parameters affecting the magnitude of spring-back.

Curved parts made of either symmetric or unsymmetric lay-up may experience spring-back. Here, focus is on the spring-back of symmetric curved laminates, and the spring-back phenomenon is examined using L-shaped elbows.

II. EXPERIMENT

Tests were conducted with L-shaped 90 degree elbows made of unidirectional graphite/epoxy prepreg tape (Figure 1). The plies were laid up on an aluminum tool which had a rounded corner. The elbow and the tool were vacuum bagged and cured by the temperatures and pressure shown in Figure 2. After cooling to room temperature, the elbows were removed from the tool and their dimensions were determined by a coordinate measurement table. Measurements were made at eighteen points on the inner surfaces of each elbow. From these measurements, the average spring-back angle \emptyset was determined (Figure 3). In addition, the thickness of each laminate was measured at several points.

III. RESULTS

Data were generated with elbows made of Fiberite T300/934 graphite/epoxy tapes. Each leg of the elbow was three inches wide and six inches long. The inside radius of the corner was either 0.5 or 0.25 inch. Tests were conducted with elbows having five distinct sets of fiber orientations:

- (1) unidirectional with the fibers in the 0 degree direction (this direction is along the axis of the elbow),
- (2) unidirectional with the fibers being in the 90 degree direction (ie. perpendicular to the axis of the elbow),
- (3) cross ply (0/90),
- (4) angle ply (± 45),
- (5) quasi-isotropic (0/ ± 45 /90).

Every layup used in this study is symmetric and encompasses those commonly used in practice.

Figure 1 Illustration of the elbow and the mold.

Figure 2 Cure cycle used in manufacturing the elbows.

Spring-back: Ø

Figure 3 Dimensions of the elbow and definition of the spring-back.

The effects on spring-back of the following five parameters were considered:

- (1) ply orientation,
- (2) position of the 0 degree ply groups,
- (3) laminate thickness,
- (4) corner radius,
- (5) fiber volume fraction.

The effect of ply orientation is illustrated in Figures 4 and 5. The layup seems to have little effect on the spring-back, at least when comparing cross ply, angle ply, and quasi-isotropic laminates. The spring-back of elbows containing plies with more than one orientation is higher than those of elbows containing only 0 or 90 degree unidirectional plies. Thus, the spring-back of elbows made of unidirectional plies does not provide an upper bound for spring-back. This is consistent with analytical results.

The effect of stacking sequence on spring-back is shown in Figure 5. As can be seen, the stacking sequence does not have a significant effect on the spring-back. This is further illustrated in Figure 6 where the spring-back of cross ply elbows is shown. Even when the location of the 0 and 90 degree layers are interchanged, the spring-back is only slightly altered.

Figure 4 The effect of ply angle on spring-back.

Figure 5 The effect of ply arrangement on spring-back.

Figure 6 The effect of the position of the 0 degree ply group on spring-back.

The effect of the laminate thickness on spring-back is illustrated in Figure 7. In this figure, the spring-back of elbows made of either 16 or 32 plies (± 45 degree) are shown. The spring-back is practically the same for the thinner and thicker elbows.

The influence of the corner radius on the spring-back is shown in Figure 8. Unfortunately, the data obtained with 0.25 in radius corners were unduly influenced by changes in fiber volume fraction. Thus, in Figure 8, analytical results are included to illustrate the effect of the radius on spring-back. As these results show, the radius of the corner has little or no effect on the value of the spring-back.

Finally, the influence on spring-back of fiber volume fraction in the corner region of the elbow is examined. The fiber volume fraction was calculated on the basis of the measured thickness at the corner of the elbow. The results presented in Figure 9 show that the fiber volume fraction has a major effect on the spring-back. An increase in the fiber volume fraction from 0.5 to 0.78 reduces the spring-back by nearly a factor of two.

Figure 7 The effect of ply thickness on spring-back.

Figure 8 The effect of corner radius on spring-back.

Figure 9 The effect of fiber volume fraction on spring-back.

IV. CONCLUDING REMARKS

The results in this paper indicate that changes in ply orientation, position of the 0 degree ply groups, laminate thickness, and corner radius do not produce significant changes in spring-back. On the other hand, fiber volume fraction has a major influence on spring-back. Since fiber volume fraction can be changed significantly during manufacturing, attention must be paid to manufacturing procedures if spring-back needs to be minimized.

Finally, it is emphasized that the results and conclusions strictly apply only under the conditions of the present tests. Although the conclusions may be extended to other circumstances, care must be exercised in extrapolation of the data.

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